

Implications of Extrinsic Motivation and Mindset in Learning

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Abstract

People's engagement, determination, and learning outcomes are substantially influenced by extrinsic incentive and mindset. This study presents insights into the factors influencing extrinsic motivation and mindset in the context of learning. It examines the various components of extrinsic motivation, including external rewards, acceptance from society, and meeting goals. The study looks at the variables that influence how someone responds to external motivations, such as how their attitude impacts how they accept challenges, seek feedback, and continue in the face of failures. Furthermore, it investigates how a person's thinking affects how they react to external motivators. Understanding the extrinsic motivation and mindset in learning is necessary to encourage meaningful engagement, long-lasting motivation, and improved learning outcomes. This study offers significant insights into the factors influencing extrinsic motivation, emphasises the significance of mindset in this process, and provides practical suggestions for future research on motivation and learning.

Keywords: Extrinsic motivation, Learning, Persistence, Growth mindset, Fixed mindset, Rewards, Feedback

1. Introduction

Extrinsic motivation and mindset are crucial when it comes to an individual's level of engagement, perseverance, and learning outcomes. To maximise learning opportunities and foster success over the long run, educators, policymakers, and researchers must have a thorough understanding of how people maintain their motivation and mindset while learning. With a thorough examination of the available literature, this research work intends to analyse the factors affecting extrinsic motivation and mindset in learning.

Mindset is closely related to theories of motivation, according to Dweck (2017). Although Deci et al. (2001) and Dweck & Master (2009) and other researchers have proposed that motivation and achievement have a reciprocal relationship, whereby academic successes and failures impact motivation and motivation in turn impacts achievement, Wigfield & Wagner (2007) added that the relationship between motivation and academic achievement has been considered to be one-directional, with motivation influencing academic achievement (Saunders, 2013). The impact of mindset on motivating factors like reaction to failure, determination and degree of effort, and expectations of success, which in turn affect academic achievement, is complicated and could be most significant.

Extrinsic motivation describes the external factors, such as rewards, recognition, or social acceptance, that encourage people to engage in activities or pursue goals. Extrinsic motivation can be a crucial element in motivating learners, even if intrinsic motivation—driven by internal

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factors—is proven to enhance long-term engagement and enjoyment of learning. To maintain motivation and encourage the best learning outcomes, it is crucial to comprehend how extrinsic motivators can be used and kept effectively.

On the other side, mindset describes people's attitudes and ideas towards their own abilities, intelligence, and possibility of development. According to C. S. Dweck (2017), Sanguras (2021) and Wormeli (2018), a growth mindset is defined by the belief that skills can be improved through hard work, perseverance, and successful strategies; it is intrinsically motivated. In contrast, a fixed mindset involves the belief that skills are fixed and unchangeable; extrinsically motivated. Mindset can have a considerable impact on an individual's responsiveness to external motivators as well as their general attitude towards learning and problems (Bedford, 2017; Ng, 2018; Sanguras, 2021; Sochan, 2012).

The findings of this study will affect both teachers and decision-makers in a practical way. The creation of productive educational practises and interventions will be influenced by knowledge of how extrinsic motivators can be used to foster sustained motivation and how mindset can be fostered to maximise learning engagement and outcomes (Bedford, 2017; Calingasan & Plata, 2022; Myers et al., 2016; Nalipay et al., 2021). This review aims to contribute to improving the quality of learning experiences and fostering a sense of long-term achievement for learners across diverse educational settings by identifying key elements that affect the extrinsic motivation and mindset.

The purpose of this study is to investigate the factors affecting learners' extrinsic motivation and mindset, as well as the reciprocal link between the two. It explores the extrinsic motivation and mindset in educational situations using current theoretical frameworks, empirical research, and practical consequences. In the context of learning, this study seeks to provide a thorough knowledge of the complex connections between extrinsic motivation and mindset.

It attempts to shed light on the learner's extrinsic motivation and learning. This study, which focuses on previous studies, aims to offer relevant details on the factors that affect the reciprocal relationship between extrinsic motivation and mindset as well as the useful implications for educational practise (Barron & Harackiewicz, 2000; Katsuhisa & Masahide, 2009). The findings will help in developing approaches to improve learner engagement and outcomes and increase knowledge in the subject.

2. *Extrinsic motivation and Mindset*

2.1 *Rewards*

It is important to take caution and deliberation while using rewards in regard to mindset. The development of a growth mindset can benefit from rewards that place an emphasis on effort, progress, and learning, as opposed to rewards that are only concerned with outcomes or fixed traits, which might work against the development

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of a growth mindset. Deci and Ryan (1985) found that people with fixed mindsets appeared to depend more on outside rewards and show higher levels of extrinsic motivation. According to Dweck and Leggett (1988), those who have a fixed mindset tend to rely more heavily on external rewards and motivation. Mueller and Dweck (1998) noted that people with a fixed mindset demonstrated a greater desire for extrinsic rewards and validation, which resulted in decreased intrinsic drive. Teachers and education policymakers can build an environment that encourage mindset development and fosters a love for learning and personal improvement by aligning with rewards and with a growth-oriented mindset and encouraging intrinsic motivation.

2.2 Recognition

In order to encourage a growth-oriented mindset, recognition has the capacity to affect mindset. It can help to foster a growth attitude when praise is given in a way that emphasises effort, growth, and the learning process. On the other hand, praise that is only given for fixed characteristics or results in performance may encourage a fixed attitude (Long et al., 2021). Individuals with a fixed mindset appeared to rely more heavily on extrinsic motivation and external validation, according to Dweck and Leggett (1988). Mueller and Dweck (1998) discovered that those with a fixed mindset depended more on extrinsic motivational factors, such praise for their success, than they did on intrinsic motivation. Teachers, education policymakers, and parents can cultivate environments that foster mindset development and inspire people to accept difficulties, persevere in their efforts, and have faith in their capacity to learn and improve by purposefully giving growth-oriented acknowledgment.

2.3 Social approval

Recognition from society has a significant impact on people's perceptions about their capacities and opportunities for improvement, which helps to shape mindset. While the absence of or negative social recognition can encourage a fixed mindset, positive social recognition that emphasises effort, progress, and improvement can foster a growth mindset. According to research done in 2007 by Blackwell, Trzesniewski, and Dweck, students who have a fixed mindset are more likely to show a preference for extrinsic rewards than students who have a growth mindset (Blackwell et al., 2007). According to research by Dweck (2000); Molden & Dweck, 2000a), those who have a fixed mindset are more prone to rely on external rewards and show higher levels of extrinsic motivation. According to a study by Blackwell, Trzesniewski, and Dweck (2007), students who have a fixed mindset are more likely to be motivated by external factors than students who have a

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development mindset. People with the fixed mindset look for their social recognition for their talent and capacity.

Promoting a growth-oriented attitude requires building a friendly and welcoming social environment that values individuals' efforts, recognises achievement, and offers constructive criticism. Teachers, policymakers, and peers can help people develop constructive attitudes and encourage them on their path to success by purposefully creating social recognition.

3. *Extrinsic Motivation and fixed Mindset*

In the study of motivation and learning, the idea of extrinsic motivation and its connection to a fixed mindset remain contentious topics.

Extrinsic motivation is required to engage in an activity or pursue a goal in response to rewards, praise, or recognition from outside sources. Extrinsic motivational factors can initially compel people to complete a task, but a person's mindset can have a long-term impact on sustainability and intrinsic drive. A increasing body of evidence suggests a connection between fixed mindset and external motivation. For instance, one study indicated that while students with a growth mindset were more inclined to put forth extra effort to understand the subject, students with a fixed mindset were more likely to cheat on a test in order to receive an appropriate mark (Yeager & Dweck, 2012). Employees with growth mindsets were more likely to persevere in the face of difficulties, according to a different study (Dweck, Chiu, & Hong, 1995). Employees with a fixed mindset were more likely to give up on challenging tasks when they received negative feedback.

A fixed mindset is the belief that one's abilities and intelligence are invariably fixed traits. People who have a fixed mindset sometimes interpret their successes and failures as proof of their innate skills, which makes them seek outside approval and shy away from difficulties that can make them question their perception of their own ability. Individuals with a fixed mindset were more prone to look for external rewards and motivations for their performance, according to Burnette, O'Boyle, VanEpps, Pollack, and Finkel (2013); According them people with a fixed mindset are more inclined to put extrinsic rewards ahead of intrinsic motivation.

There are a number of issues when looking at extrinsic motivation in people with fixed mindsets (Ferguson, 2017; Nalipay et al., 2021; Sanguras, 2021; Yu & McLellan, 2020). In the beginning, those with a fixed mindset could depend more on rewards and approval from others to stay motivated. Their interest in activities or tasks is primarily motivated by extrinsic rewards, such as grades or praise. Their intrinsic drive may decline in the absence of these external motivators, which could reduce their willingness to keep going or participate in learning activities.

Furthermore, those who have a fixed mindset often pay more attention to the result and outside assessment than the actual learning process (Degol et al., 2018; Nalipay et al., 2021; Sanguras,

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2021; Yu & McLellan, 2020). They could be more motivated to focus on getting good grades or getting rewards than on enjoying the learning process or overcoming to difficulties that might help them progress. Their capacity to cultivate intrinsic motivation and a sincere love of learning may be constrained by their focus on external objectives.

The fixed mindset affects how people view failures or setbacks and react to them. They would interpret such failures as proof of their inability, which would erode their motivation and resilience. According to Hochanadel and Finamore (2015), the fear of failure might further discourage people from taking chances or looking for new challenges, which may retard growth and development.

Individuals with a fixed mindset can be affected by their reliance on outside rewards and recognition, their emphasis on goal-oriented outcomes, and how they interpret failures. In order to address this, professionals and educators should think about methods that foster intrinsic drive and a growth mindset. People with a fixed mindset can be assisted in developing a more flexible and adaptable attitude to their motivation by offering opportunities for learning and growth, emphasising the process rather than just the outcome, and creating a supportive and nurturing learning environment. Teachers can improve the long-term retention of extrinsic motivation and assist students in their attempt to become self-motivated, lifelong learners by addressing the fixed mindset.

4. Intrinsic Motivation and Growth mindset

A person's ability to learn, achieve, and develop personally is greatly influenced by their intrinsic motivation and growth mindset. The relationship between intrinsic motivation and growth mindset.

When people engage in an activity for its own sake, without regard to rewards or encouragement from others, they are said to be motivated intrinsically. Personal interest, curiosity, and the intrinsic satisfaction gained from the learning and mastery processes serve as its sources of energy. People that engage in things because of intrinsic motivation do so because they perceive such activities to be personally rewarding, enjoyable, or significant (Burton & Dweck, 2020).

On the other hand, growth mindset is the belief that one's abilities and intelligence can be developed through effort, effective strategies, and persistence. Individuals with a growth mindset embrace challenges, view setbacks as opportunities for learning and growth, and believe in the potential to improve and expand their skills and knowledge. They focus on the process of learning, value effort, and are not discouraged by initial difficulties or failures (C. S. Dweck, 2017)

Contrarily, a growth mindset is the belief that one's skills and intelligence can be improved with effort, sensible approaches, and determination. People who have a growth mindset

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welcome challenge, see failures as chances for learning and development, and have faith in their ability to advance and broaden their knowledge and skills. They value effort, keep their attention on the learning process, and aren't discouraged by early challenges or setbacks (C. S. Dweck, 2017).

Growth mindset and intrinsic motivation are interrelated and reinforce one another. People who have a growth mindset are more likely to be intrinsically motivated. According to study by Blackwell, Trzesniewski, and Dweck from 2007, students who have a growth mindset are more likely to exhibit high levels of intrinsic motivation than students who have a fixed mindset (Blackwell et al., 2007). According to a study by Dweck (2000), those who have a growth mindset are more likely to show higher levels of intrinsic motivation. A growth mindset is positively correlated with intrinsic motivation and the drive to learn, according to Dweck (2012).

Their internal motivation to look for new challenges, pick up new knowledge, and improve their talents is driven by the belief in their capacity for improvement and growth. As people engage in activities motivated by curiosity, enthusiasm, and the desire for personal improvement, this intrinsic motivation in turn reinforces and enhances their growth mindset. Yeager and Dweck (2012) discovered through their research that students who had a growth mindset were more likely to have higher levels of intrinsic motivation and a passion for learning. Students that have a growth mindset showed more intrinsic desire for their academic work, according to Haimovitz and Dweck (2016).

Growth mindset and intrinsic motivation work well together in numerous ways. First of all, intrinsic motivation keeps people interested in and committed to learning. People who are intrinsically motivated are more likely to persevere through difficulties, look for more learning opportunities, and put in the necessary time and effort to learn new ideas or abilities. This determination is consistent with the growth mindset theory, which holds that effort and successful strategies result in advancement and success (Degol et al., 2018; Myers et al., 2016; Nalipay et al., 2021; Ng, 2018). Second, by promoting a passion for learning, intrinsic motivation helps in the establishment of a growth mindset. People are more likely to adopt a growth mindset and embrace lifelong learning when they experience true delight and happiness in the learning process itself. According to research by Bieg et al. (2011), Kormos et al. (2011), Tsai (1991), and Wolters & Rosenthal (2000) intrinsic motivation encourages people to pursue knowledge and skills for their own satisfaction and continuous growth.

Teachers and other professionals play a crucial role in encouraging intrinsic motivation and a growth mindset. People's intrinsic motivation can be increased by creating a supportive and interesting learning environment that promotes autonomy, proficiency, and purpose (Bieg et al., 2011; C. S. Dweck, 1986; Elliot & McGregor, 1999; Kormos et al., 2011; Zhao et al., 2018). People can pursue topics and endeavours that connect to their interests and passions by having opportunities for choice, autonomy, and self-directed learning. Additionally, encouraging a

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growth-oriented classroom culture that values effort, views errors as teaching opportunities, and offers helpful criticism can aid in the establishment of a growth mindset.

Intrinsic motivation and growth mindset are closely intertwined and mutually reinforcing. When individuals experience intrinsic motivation, driven by personal interest and enjoyment, they are more likely to embrace a growth mindset and engage in continuous learning and improvement. Nurturing intrinsic motivation and fostering a growth mindset create a powerful combination that promotes resilience, a love for learning, and the belief in the potential for growth and success.

5. *Key Factors Influencing the Retention of Extrinsic Motivation and Development of Growth Mindset*

5.1 Motivation Retention: Long-term engagement, persistence, and learning outcomes are facilitated by maintaining extrinsic motivation and establishing a growth mindset. For educators, policymakers, and researchers looking to enhance learning opportunities and foster academic success, understanding the key factors that affect the retention of extrinsic motivation and the development of a growth mindset is essential (C. Dweck, 2019; C. S. Dweck, 1986; Kormos et al., 2011; Nalipay et al., 2021; Wolters & Rosenthal, 2000).

5.2 Clear and Challenging Goals: Setting definite, challenging targets is essential for sustaining external motivation and promoting a growth mindset. Goals that are clearly defined provide students a sense of direction and purpose, while demanding goals motivate them to work hard. Learners are more likely to maintain their motivation and develop a growth mindset by viewing challenges as opportunities for growth and improvement if extrinsic motivators, such as rewards or recognition, are matched with these goals (Bostwick et al., 2020; DeBacker et al., 2018; Ebenezer Nrumah et al., 2021; Lim & Ryu, 2019; Yu & McLellan, 2020).

5.3 Supportive Learning Environment: The establishment of a growth mindset and the retention of extrinsic motivation are strongly influenced by the learning environment. Positive teacher-student interactions, opportunities for collaborative learning, and a focus on effort and growth rather than just results are examples of elements that make up an environment that is encouraging. Because they view their skills as malleable and build resilience in the face of difficulties when they feel supported, encouraged, and valued, learners are more likely to maintain their extrinsic motivation and adopt a growth mindset (Fretz, 2021; Huang et al., 2019; Koul et al., 2012; Müller & Louw, 2004; Velayutham et al., 2013).

5.3 Meaningful and Relevant Learning Experiences: Learners' intrinsic motivation is increased and their growth mindset is fostered when they participate in relevant and significant learning experiences. They see the significance and relevance of their

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effort when they connect it to practical applications, personal interests, or long-term goals. According to several studies (Fretz, 2021; Huang et al., 2019; Müller & Louw, 2004; Tas, 2016; Velayutham et al., 2013), offering opportunities for hands-on tasks, problem-solving, and authentic assessments can improve motivation and mindset development.

5.4 Effective Feedback and Recognition: Retaining extrinsic motivation and encouraging a growth mindset depend on giving quick, precise, and constructive feedback. Feedback that emphasises effort, development, and the strategies employed rather than just performance outcomes helps students believe they can get better. By affirming learners' progress and potential, acknowledging their achievements both intrinsically and extrinsically boosts their motivation and fosters a growth mindset (Ashford & De Stobbeleir, 2013; Carless et al., 2011; Krenn et al., 2013; Senko & Harackiewicz, 2005).

5.5 Modelling and Encouragement: The motivation and mindset of students can be influenced by modelling a growth mindset and offering encouragement. Learners are more likely to embrace and internalise growth mindset concepts when teachers, classmates, and role models do so through welcoming difficulties, appreciating effort, and persisting through failures. By highlighting the value of effort and progress, encouragement and positive reinforcement help learners enhance their motivation and mindset (Huang et al., 2019; Müller & Louw, 2004; Sökmen, 2021; Velayutham et al., 2013).

5.6 Cultivating Self-Efficacy: Self-efficacy, or having trust in one's ability for achievement in particular activities or fields, has an intricate connection to both extrinsic motivation and mindset formation. Fostering learners' self-efficacy involves offering them chances to practise competency, providing appropriate scaffolding and support, and promoting self-reflection and self-evaluation. Learners are more likely to maintain their motivation and develop a growth mindset when they believe in their ability to succeed and attribute their successes to their efforts and strategies (Ajzen, 2002; Chen & Shane Tutwiler, 2017; Chen & Tutwiler, 2017; Gallagher, 2012; Schunk & DiBenedetto, 2021; Uçar & Sungur, 2017).

5.7 Growth-Oriented Language and Mindset Interventions: Extrinsic motivation and the development of a growth mindset can be considerably impacted by the use of growth-oriented language and mindset interventions. Learners internalise the idea that abilities may be developed when they are encouraged to put out effort, grow, and learn from their failures (Calingasan & Plata, 2022; Mueller & Dweck, 1998; Pomerantz & Kempner, 2013). Mindset interventions have been demonstrated to have a favourable impact on learners' motivation and mindset (Manchi Chao et al., 2017; Miller, 2019;

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Orosz et al., 2017; Yeager et al., 2016). These interventions include teaching about the plasticity of the brain and offering ways to overcome obstacles.

As a result, a number of significant factors affect the formation of a growth mindset as well as extrinsic motivation. In order to develop motivation and a growth mindset, it is essential to have clear, challenging goals, a supportive learning environment, meaningful learning experiences, effective feedback and recognition, modelling and encouragement, cultivating self-efficacy, and growth-oriented language and interventions. Learning outcomes can be improved and long-term academic success can be facilitated by educators and policymakers establishing environments that foster sustained motivation, resilience, and a growth mindset.

6. Conclusion

The study on extrinsic motivation and how it interacts with mindset in learning sheds light on the intricate relationship between external rewards and people's perceptions of their own prospective and ability. In order to maximise learning outcomes and encourage lifelong learning, the study emphasises the significance of taking both extrinsic motivation and attitude into account in educational environments.

Extrinsic motivation in the form of rewards may at first increase performance and engagement, but the study's findings indicate that its long-term effects on learning and motivation depend on people's mindsets. A growth mindset, which is characterised by a belief that abilities can be improved via effort and learning, can help people get more long-lasting benefits from extrinsic motivators. The impact of extrinsic motivation may be limited and the growth of intrinsic drive and a love of learning could be hindered by a fixed mindset, which sees abilities as fixed attributes.

The results of this study have important significance for teachers, administrators, and experts of the field of education. It emphasises the necessity of encouraging learners to adopt a growth mindset by establishing a learning environment that rewards drive, resilience, and confidence in one's own ability to improve. It also implies that extrinsic motivators, like rewards and recognition, can work well to encourage participation and performance, especially when they are in line with a mindset that is focused on one's own growth.

Extrinsic motivation and a growth mindset can be developed simultaneously through educational interventions and practices. Instead of focusing simply on grades or other external outcomes, instructors can, for instance, give students meaningful feedback that is both particular and meaningful and that emphasises effort, improvement, and progress. They can also give students the chance to define their own goals, reflect on their own actions, and gain a sense of autonomy and intrinsic motivation.

The study's conclusion points out how important it is for educational environments to take into account extrinsic motivation and mindset. The extrinsic motivation of students can be

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improved, a growth mindset can be encouraged, and students' journeys towards lifelong learning and academic success can ultimately be supported by educators by understanding the reciprocal relationship between these components and putting into practice effective techniques.

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